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Gravity is transduced through the Hippo signaling pathway.

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We describe here gravity as a mechanical force that is exerted on human cells and tissues, which we demonstrate through experimental manipulation of gravity, is transduced through sensing of mechanical force through the Hippo signal transduction pathway.

Results

We measured total transcription to understand the most significant changes in gene expression following experimental manipulation of gravitational forces (gravity).

Since YAP and TAZ transmit signals (i.e., mechanotransduction) from the ECM to the nucleus, we first examined changes in Hippo pathway signaling, and changes in expression of key members of the extracellular matrix which convert applied force (i.e., tension) to a signal for transmission to the nucleus. Genes involved in transducing signals through the Hippo pathway include YAP, TAZ, MOB1/2, STK25, TEAD genes, MAP4Ks, and salvador (SAV1).

Figure 1: Changes in gravitational force result in activation of TEAD2 and STK25, components of the Hippo signal transduction pathway.

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n=3 MG63 cultured osteosarcoma cells exposed to microgravity (34 hours +/-1 hr)

n=2 MG63 cultured osteosarcoma cells exposed gravity at 1g (34 hours +/-1 hr)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
60485	1.66e-16	0.1264	8.244654	1.0420173	1062.38	SAV1	350/ 21381	98.4
8463	2.76e-10	0.1476	-6.3117269	-0.9315993	665.48	TEAD2	856/21381	
10494	1.39e-03	0.1208	-3.1968073	-0.3861482	1823.28	STK25	4155/21381	

Exposure to changes in gravitational force resulted in activation of SAV1, as well as repression of TEAD2 and STK25.

Exposing cells to changes in the gravitational force resulted in changes in expression of ECM components, including integrins, cell adhesion molecules and junctional molecules, indicating involvement of mechanical processes in processes and alterations of the cell following or resulting from exposure to changes in gravitational force.

Figure 2: Changes in gravitational force result in activation of CDH15, as well as repression of cadherins CDH6 and FAT4.

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1013	3.09e-14	0.2759	7.5945791	2.0952456	241.62	CDH15	480/	
1004	1.06e-13	0.179	-7.4330448	-1.3308059	2696.42	CDH6	521	
79633	3.50e-12	0.1463	-6.9558361	-1.0176142	507.58	FAT4	650	

Figure 3: Changes in gravitational force result in changes in expression junctional and vesicular transport genes.

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
9414	3.91e-09	0.1484	-5.8881299	-0.8738227	452.78	TJP2	1045/	
857	4.14e-46	0.1247	-14.2555413	-1.7771784	7669.8	CAV1	23/	
858	1.61e-16	0.1351	-8.248133	-1.1141098	948.49	CAV2	349/	

Among the most significant changes in transcription across the transcriptomes of cells exposed to microgravity, we observed what appears to be a relationship between gravitational force and cellular proliferation.

Figure 4: Changes in gravitational force result in changes in expression of genes involved in proliferation.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
4288	1.01e-14	0.2009	-7.7379547	-1.5545697	7918.24	MKI67	449/	
2146	3.62e-17	0.1643	-8.4246874	-1.3839612	541.18	EZH2	320/	
7083	9.46e-21	0.1674	-9.3419789	-1.5634321	1133.24	TK1	189/	
1894	8.25e-16	0.1084	-8.0504716	-0.8723098	4415.06	ECT2	387/	
5111	3.74e-10	0.1699	-6.2643141	-1.0643846	1362.38	PCNA	881/	
7153	9.34e-31	0.1132	-11.5297996	-1.3047133	9450.58	TOP2A	63/	

We found activation and repression of genes functioning in DNA damage signaling associated with differences in gravitational force.

Figure 5: Changes in gravitational force result in differential expression of genes involved in DNA damage signaling and DNA repair.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
55355	9.71e-18	0.151	-8.5773508	-1.2951666	2420.32	HJURP	297/	
348654	1.50e-16	0.1696	-8.2567348	-1.400569	980.76	GEN1	348/	
7516	2.78e-17	0.1733	-8.4553827	-1.4650463	578.95	XRCC2	311/	

We observed changes in expression of polarity-associated genes under micro-gravitational force.

Figure 6: Changes in polarity-associated genes following exposure to changes in gravitational force.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
84612	6.81e-16	0.1988	8.0738207	1.6054527	426.56	PAR6B	381/	
81839	5.72e-11	0.1375	-6.5508945	-0.9004528	1612.81	VANGL1	774/	
8825	6.66e-10	0.1379	-6.1739107	-0.851146	1341.72	LIN7A	920/	

Finally, we discovered changes in expression of genes of the caspase family, and genes involved in telomere function following exposure of human cells to changes in gravitational force

Figure 7: Changes in expression of caspases and telomere-associated genes in human cells resulting from manipulation of gravitational force.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
837	6.92e-28	0.1198	10.9463213	1.3110039	1696.98	CASP4	87/	
835	5.61e-10	0.1255	-6.2010166	-0.7780125	986.27	CASP2	907/	

Figure 7: Changes in expression of caspases and telomere-associated genes in human cells resulting from manipulation of gravitational force.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
9894	1.61e-09	0.1373	-6.0330808	-0.8281937	1091.25	TELO2	987/	
163859	6.55e-09	0.1304	5.8019731	0.7565501	2523.54	SDE2	1095/	
51750	9.94e-07	0.1491	-4.8927943	-0.729637	862.26	RTEL1	1691/	
7012	1.63e-05	0.1475	4.3109488	0.6358546	723.51	TERC	2304/21381	89.2

Discussion

We described here activation and repression of genes of the Hippo signaling pathway, which senses mechanical force in the ECM and transduces this to the nucleus, following exposure to changes in gravitational force, indicating the importance of this pathway in effecting homeostatic control of force and pressure from the atmosphere, in which gravity is a important shaping force. We used whole transcriptome methods to measure total expression in human cells, using experimental manipulation of gravitational force to expose human cells to changes in the amount of mechanical force exerted and sensed by cells resulting from the force of gravity.

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